

ANALYSIS OF RAINFALL PATTERN FOR ANJAR TALUKA OF KUTCH DISTRICT – GUJARAT STATE

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ABSTRACT

The rainfall in Kutch District is very scanty and irregular and the district has very few rainy days. The average annual rainfall in the district is between 300 mm to 400 mm. The number of rainy days varies between 10 days to 17 days.

The Lakhpat taluka is located in the central mainland of Kutch district. The region mostly consists of sandy clay soil. It has a geographical area of 121580 hectares. The average annual rainfall for Anjar is 345 mm as against 356 mm average annual rainfall of Kutch district.

Through this paper it is attempted to study the Rainfall Pattern for Anjar taluka and compare it with that of Kutch district. For this purpose, annual rainfall data for a period of 130 years from 1878 to 2007 is studied and the probabilities of occurrence and dry and wet spells for the taluka as well as the region have been determined.

ABOUT THE STUDY AREA

Kutch is an ancient land possessed of great antiquity, which takes its name from its geographical characteristics and topographical features resembling a tortoise. This crescent shaped region forms part of the northwest Gujarat.

The district stretches roughly from 22°44'11" (approx.) to 24°41'25" (approx.) north latitudes and 68°09'46" (approx.) and 71°54'47" (approx.) east longitudes. It is bounded on the north and north-west by Sindh (Pakistan), on the north-east by Rajasthan, on the east by the districts of Banaskantha and Mehsana, on the south-east by Surendranagar district, on the south by the Gulf of Kutch and the Rajkot district and on the south-west and west by the Arabian Sea. The district is roughly divided into four parts i.e Kutch mainland, Wagad region, Island belt comprising of four islands in the desert region and the Rann portion. Rapar taluka is a part of the Wagad region of Kutch.

The Anjar taluka is located 23°08'N 70°01'E / 23.13°N 70.02°E / 23.13; 70.02. The taluka of Anjar is situated towards the south east of the mainland of Kutch. It has an average elevation of 81 metres (265 feet). It is situated nearly 10 miles from the Gulf of Kutch. The region is dry and sandy, and entirely depends on well irrigation for its water supply.. It includes a town of the same name (Anjar) and 59 main villages in the block. According to the 2001-Census, the total population of the district was 1,526,321 inhabitants. The total population of Anjar city is estimated to be 344,783 or 39.54% of the total population of the district. Anjar experienced additional significant quakes 21 July 1956 and 26 January 2001.

Lakhpata	23° 49"	68° 47"
year	LAKHPAT	
Area IN M2	2386428606	
area in km2	2386.428606	
Perimeter	319949.024	
Hectares	238642.861	

Figure 1 Location map for Kutch District and Bhuj taluka

Rainfall

The normal rainfall for Kutch district ranges between 300 to 400 mm. The district receives an average annual rainfall of 356 mm (for study period of 1878 to 2007), which is erratic and depends on the strength of the summer monsoon. It ranges from 335 mm at Bhuj to 452 mm at Naliya. It varies from 408 mm at Mandvi on the southern coast to 250 mm at Lakhpata on the northwest coast. The variation in the annual rainfall from the year to year is very large. The monsoon rains usually set in by the third week of June in the coastal belt and withdraws by the end of September. The maximum rainfall takes place during the month of July and very less rain occurs during the month of August and September. Most of annual rainfall in the district is received during the southwest monsoon season, July being the rainiest month. Rainfall of about 178 to 468 mm in a single day has also been recorded at many stations.

The average annual rainfall for Anjar taluka is 345 mm. Table 1 shows the annual rainfall for Anjar taluka as well as Kutch district for the period 1878 to 2007. It includes the analysis using moving mean method. Three year and five year moving mean values have been calculated for Anjar taluka as well as Kutch district. During period 1878 to 2007 the highest annual rainfall amounting to 996 mm for Kutch district occurred in the year 1959 and 1060 mm for Anjar taluka in the year 1967. Figure 2 shows the bar graphs and 3 year and 5 year moving mean graphs for Anjar taluka as well as Kutch district.

5.3 SOILS OF KUTCH

The soils of Kutch can be mainly classified into:

- (1) Clayey
- (2) Sandy clay
- (3) Clayey medium black
- (4) Sandy clayey and medium black

Though other types such as loamy, silty and clayey are also found at certain places, the northern part of the district is dominated by desert and sandy soils which are mostly salt affected soils. Proceeding southwards, the interior area is composed of either sandy or medium black soils. The southern part of the district comprising the coastal area around Mandvi and Mundra has saline soils suitable for cultivation. The eastern part is mostly plain with some rocky patches where the soil is sandy with clay and alluvial loam in some parts. The central portion is hilly and rocky with strips of cultivable lands along the lower slopes. The soil is poor but due to better underground water currents in this part the irrigation facilities are adequate. In the western part, the soils are mostly sandy with patches of fine sandy loams having no scope for well irrigation. The soils in Kutch are generally poor in plant nutrients and lime content in most of them is quite high. Table 5.2 shows the talukawise distribution of the type of soils. The distribution of the type of soil for all the talukas has been shown in Figure 5.7.

Figure 5.7 Map showing types of Soils in Kutch

Table 5.2 Types of Soils

Type of Soil	Taluka
Clayey	Mundra
Sandy Clay	Bhuj, Anjar Rapar Nakhatrana
Clayey & Medium black	Lakhpat Mandvi Abdasa
Sandy, Clayey & Medium Black	Bhachau

5.5 OPEN WELLS IN KUTCH

Gujarat Water Resources Development Corporation (GWRDC) has set up several observation wells, tubewells and piezometers in Kutch. Observations for the pre-monsoon and post-monsoon for ground water table have been considered for the purpose of the study for the period 1989 to 2007. Figure 5.12 shows the location of the observation wells for Kutch district. The details of the locations of the wells for each taluka have been given in the alphabetical order of the names of the talukas.

Figure 5.12 Map showing locations of Observation Open wells (Source: GWRDC)

5.5.4 Lakhpat Taluka

The general details of the open wells for Lakhpat taluka are as follows.

Basin: West Coast Minor

Geology: Alluvial

Rainfall Station: Lakhpat

Stratigraphy: Recent to Sub Recent

Table 5.6 Details of Open wells for Lakhpat Taluka

Village	Sub Basin	Minor Basin	Geology	Latitude	Longitude	Height of Measuring Point	R.L. in M	Stratigraphy
Narayan sarovar	Kori creek	Local Basal tin	Limestone	23°40'35"	68°32'32"	1.35	9.03	Pleistocene
Panandhro	Kali	Kali	Limestone	23°41'17"	60°45'05"	0.40	38.90	Pleistocene
Chher Moti	Kapuras	Kapuras	Limestone	23°45'59"	68°38'40"	1.20	10.91	Pleistocene

Lakhpata	Naira	Naira	Limestone	23°50'31"	68°46'51"	1.30	13.12	Pleistocene
Gadhuli	Kali	Kankavati	Sandstone	23°41'51"	68°53'16"	0.00	103.61	Cretaceous
Dolatpar	Kali	Chokk	Sandstone	23°35'51"	68°53'16"	0.60	117.05	Cretaceous

5.6 TUBE WELLS IN KUTCH

The groundwater level for pre-monsoon and post-monsoon for the tubewells has been obtained from 1989 to 2008. Figure 5.13 and Figure 5.14 shows the location of the observation tubewells and observation piezometers for Kutch district. The details of the locations of the wells for each taluka have been given in the alphabetical order of the names of the talukas.

Figure 5.13 Map showing locations of Observation Tubewells (Source: GWRDC)

Table 5.21 Average Pre-Monsoon Water Levels For All Talukas

Taluka	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpatt	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakhatrana	Naliya	Rapar
May-89	25.76	25.18	56.13	41.82	44.18	24.87	81.12	34.50	34.93
May-90	31.03	32.79	46.54	40.43	41.19	24.85	76.52	35.00	40.78
May-91	26.63	25.18	54.42	40.97	42.21	24.50	79.04	34.77	34.53
May-92	26.33	23.87	54.45	40.31	47.13	35.55	78.75	33.82	33.76

May-93	28.81	28.90	56.42	41.44	45.95	25.94	79.54	34.58	34.96
May-94	24.93	27.52	51.61	38.38	42.70	30.18	78.42	31.37	31.79
May-95	28.37	28.17	53.76	39.59	36.75	23.97	80.86	35.56	35.55
May-96	22.90	23.49	48.62	38.17	41.52	32.15	71.68	32.95	31.95
May-97	24.22	21.79	49.59	33.89	41.51	30.22	71.86	27.75	32.65
May-98	23.49	20.96	47.92	32.86	40.79	30.23	69.95	32.57	31.79
May-99	26.68	25.14	55.07	41.39	45.79	25.89	79.34	35.02	34.42
May-00	25.03	25.96	53.36	39.38	37.90	21.10	80.05	33.09	32.70
May-01	24.93	27.52	51.61	38.38	42.70	30.18	78.42	31.37	31.79
May-02	24.85	27.21	50.67	39.38	43.45	29.38	77.47	32.78	32.01
May-03	23.26	27.51	49.28	37.16	37.33	26.61	73.75	30.05	30.94
May-04	22.90	23.49	48.61	38.32	41.51	32.15	71.67	33.15	31.95
May-05	24.01	21.08	50.30	34.03	40.58	29.82	74.67	33.44	31.74
May-06	22.87	20.09	48.24	33.22	38.10	28.09	70.21	31.77	31.21
May-07	23.49	20.96	47.91	33.06	40.79	30.22	69.94	32.81	31.79

Table 5.22 Average Post-Monsoon Water Levels For All Talukas

Taluka	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpat	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakhatrana	Naliya	Rapar
Oct-88	27.90	27.56	45.14	39.98	42.58	24.05	73.11	35.58	35.46
Oct-89	24.80	24.66	53.09	39.96	44.66	31.45	79.12	32.97	34.10
Oct-90	31.85	33.07	46.16	41.41	41.13	25.16	77.10	35.53	41.31
Oct-91	26.03	23.23	54.35	39.14	42.61	24.18	78.76	36.05	33.47
Oct-92	27.36	25.20	55.44	41.15	45.65	26.16	79.37	34.45	34.09
Oct-93	24.97	25.94	53.51	39.29	38.62	22.25	80.05	32.97	32.70
Oct-94	25.01	24.14	51.37	39.52	44.93	32.86	78.87	32.99	32.64
Oct-95	30.49	28.62	54.75	40.17	37.84	25.11	81.76	36.39	36.30
Oct-96	24.81	27.51	48.86	38.40	41.65	31.65	71.66	32.91	32.65
Oct-97	22.87	20.09	48.25	33.08	38.11	28.09	70.22	31.59	31.21
Oct-98	19.84	20.61	49.51	33.88	42.49	33.73	70.90	31.46	33.48
Oct-99	28.81	28.90	56.42	41.44	45.95	25.94	79.54	34.58	34.96
Oct-00	25.91	24.38	54.27	40.25	37.59	22.31	79.72	33.58	26.00
Oct-01	25.01	24.14	51.37	39.56	44.92	32.86	78.87	33.07	32.64
Oct-02	23.95	25.94	48.95	37.80	43.43	28.93	74.21	31.51	32.06
Oct-03	25.69	27.24	53.04	39.51	43.21	34.34	75.49	30.08	33.27
Oct-04	24.81	27.51	48.86	38.49	41.65	31.64	71.66	33.02	32.65
Oct-05	24.22	21.79	49.59	34.04	41.51	30.22	71.85	27.95	32.65
Oct-06	24.57	21.83	49.65	34.54	42.12	31.63	71.23	31.53	33.55
Oct-07	19.84	20.61	49.50	34.01	42.49	33.73	70.89	31.66	33.48

5.8 GROUNDWATER WITHDRAWAL

5.8.1 Formations of The Area

There are three main types of formations for groundwater recharge in Kutch district i.e. hard rock, alluvium and sandstone. The distribution of these three formations for all the district along with the net suitable area for recharge and the specific yield of these formations was obtained from GWRDC. Table 5.23 shows the values for specific yield for all the formations for all the talukas. Table 5.24 shows the areas for alluvium, hard rock and sandstone as well as the average specific yield and the net suitable area for recharge for all the talukas.

Table 5.23 Specific Yield for all the talukas

Specific Yield In %	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpat	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakhatrana	Naliya	Rapar
Hard Rock	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.10	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Alluvium	0.18	0.10	0.15	0.10	0.15	0.10	0.15	0.10	0.10
Sandstone	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.07	0.10	0.08	0.05

Table 5.24 Distribution Of Areas For Various Formations For All Talukas

Taluka	Alluvial Area In Sq.Km.	Hard Rock Area In Sq.Km.	Sandstone Area In Sq.Km.	Average Specific Yield	Total Suitable Area In Sq.Km.
Anjar	188.00	0.00	370.25	0.13	558.25
Bhachau	0.00	0.00	499.60	0.10	499.60
Bhuj	0.00	0.00	2532.00	0.10	2532.00
Lakhpat	0.00	75.00	224.00	0.08	299.00
Mandvi	287.49	498.75	176.03	0.12	962.27
Mundra	150.65	403.80	48.00	0.04	602.45
Nakhatrana	0.00	0.00	989.90	0.10	989.90
Naliya	100.00	0.00	140.00	0.09	240.00
Rapar	0.00	0.00	997.60	0.05	997.60

5.8.2 Groundwater Water Extracting Mechanism

The data for the number of wells as well as the quantity of groundwater withdrawal was obtained from GWRDC. The data given by GWRDC was at every five year interval starting from the year 1984 to 2007. However, as the data regarding the number of wells for the years 1984 and 1991 was not available, the data for the years 1997, 2002 and 2007 was utilized and the number of wells for all the talukas were interpolated based on this data for the study period of 1989 to 2007. The details for the number of wells as well as the groundwater withdrawal for all the talukas as obtained from GWRDC has been shown in Table 10.7 in Annexure. Table 5.25 shows the number of wells obtained after interpolation of the given data for the study period.

Table 5.25 Number Of Wells For All Talukas

Year	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpat	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakhatrana	Naliya	Rapar
1989	2686	2776	5744	627	4122	2786	2653	804	4527
1990	2707	2797	5787	631	4153	2807	2673	810	4562
1991	2727	2818	5831	636	4184	2828	2693	816	4596
1992	2747	2839	5874	641	4215	2849	2713	822	4630
1993	2767	2860	5917	646	4246	2870	2733	828	4664
1994	2788	2881	5961	650	4277	2891	2753	834	4698
1995	2808	2902	6004	655	4308	2912	2773	840	4732
1996	2828	2923	6047	660	4339	2933	2793	846	4766
1997	2849	2944	6091	665	4371	2954	2814	853	4801
1998	2622	2735	5839	632	3987	2782	2533	884	4660
1999	2396	2526	5587	599	3603	2609	2252	915	4519
2000	2169	2317	5336	566	3218	2437	1972	946	4379
2001	1943	2108	5084	533	2834	2264	1691	977	4238
2002	1716	1899	4832	500	2450	2092	1410	1008	4097
2003	1929	1853	4767	419	2305	1878	1961	896	3397
2004	2141	1807	4702	338	2160	1664	2513	783	2696
2005	2354	1762	4638	258	2016	1450	3064	671	1996
2006	2566	1716	4573	177	1871	1236	3616	558	1295
2007	2779	1670	4508	96	1726	1022	4167	446	595

5.8.3 Groundwater Withdrawal Pattern

The groundwater withdrawal pattern or draft was obtained from GWRDC at every five year interval from 1984, 1991, 1997, 2002 and 2007. Based on those values a relationship for determining the draft pattern was worked out using multiple regression with the help of the software Statistica. After number of permutations and combinations for the determining the variables giving significant impact of the draft value, the following relationship was obtained.

$$Dr = .0062*W + .0721*P_{m-2} + .0198*P_{m-1} - .0185*P_m + .00047*A_{ag} - 0.0000795*A_t$$

Where, Dr = depth of draft in mm

W = water extracting mechanisms / wells in the taluka

m = number of year

P_{m-2} = Depth of Rainfall two years ago in mm

P_{m-1} = Depth of Rainfall for previous year in mm

P_m = Depth of Rainfall for current year in mm

A_{ag} = Total agricultural area in the taluka in hectares

A_t = Total area of taluka in hectares

It was found that the rainfall pattern of the previous two years played a very significant role in the draft pattern for the current year besides the number of wells, the total agricultural area and

the total area of the taluka. Table 5.26 shows the value of the draft derived for all the talukas for the study period of 1989 to 2007.

Table 5.26 derived values for Groundwater Draft in mm

Year	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpata	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakhatrana	Naliya	Rapar
1989	38.65	15.48	21.87	0.78	35.60	33.32	26.79	4.98	10.40
1990	64.57	53.85	77.86	30.96	101.11	80.92	75.89	88.77	30.03
1991	61.11	53.80	74.75	38.76	92.11	66.93	61.97	76.78	36.87
1992	38.51	34.12	31.96	-1.12	31.38	36.97	24.51	3.66	28.87
1993	42.89	24.66	34.19	16.76	52.63	51.49	40.91	20.03	22.75
1994	47.34	12.46	41.28	38.90	72.45	59.70	64.63	45.15	29.74
1995	54.25	30.22	39.40	14.63	54.01	48.50	45.24	10.02	38.53
1996	99.53	70.76	82.16	52.34	108.00	112.74	96.75	51.33	58.55
1997	34.33	24.66	27.99	5.88	43.64	36.06	26.28	31.67	22.17
1998	49.75	35.13	28.65	9.60	43.65	40.09	33.50	19.08	41.95
1999	81.92	52.00	52.49	28.68	72.61	78.34	52.39	19.98	61.41
2000	43.18	44.30	42.04	7.58	62.05	53.65	30.34	3.10	43.26
2001	29.65	33.85	21.36	3.20	33.33	24.50	20.90	0.51	20.12
2002	41.75	16.28	34.42	1.93	40.44	37.69	13.37	22.54	19.17
2003	30.69	0.94	12.44	-20.67	41.05	36.18	-0.15	29.47	3.03
2004	46.46	27.59	45.55	27.33	41.37	40.64	48.42	30.60	29.02
2005	89.41	49.24	114.19	99.71	59.05	87.65	106.18	67.46	71.95
2006	48.32	28.92	22.98	10.28	40.01	46.49	31.68	6.01	19.75
2007	53.74	32.06	26.34	14.64	38.97	53.08	48.44	20.32	15.89

5.9 RECHARGE CALCULATIONS

The groundwater recharge occurring due to rainfall as well as that occurring due to surface storage has been calculated. The total recharge is taken as the sum of the recharge due to rainfall as well as the recharge due to surface storage.

5.9.1 Recharge Due To Rainfall

The average groundwater levels obtained for pre-monsoon and post-monsoon have been used to work out the recharge due to the rainfall. The difference in the groundwater levels for post-monsoon and pre-monsoon has been multiplied by the average specific yield value for the taluka to find out the change in groundwater level in mm for all the talukas. The value for change in groundwater level in mm has been then multiplied by the fraction obtained by the ratio of the area suitable for recharge to the total area of the taluka i.e net suitable area fraction to obtain the recharge depth in mm due to the rainfall. The recharge depth thus calculated for all the talukas has been tabulated in Table 5.27. The values for recharge depth obtained for the years 1991, 1996 and 2002 are negative indicating fall in the groundwater level for those years. This fall may be a result of excessive withdrawal of groundwater during those years.

Table 5.27 Groundwater Recharge Depth in mm due to Rainfall

Year	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpata	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakhatrana	Naliya	Rapar
1989	44.37	28.80	76.13	20.07	126.67	33.67	96.46	11.40	20.51
1990	32.43	13.12	32.98	7.87	17.99	18.33	29.15	4.42	11.50
1991	13.86	-0.35	2.72	0.22	8.15	0.30	5.58	0.84	-4.55
1992	90.93	67.03	189.25	46.00	213.34	73.76	165.25	27.99	29.92
1993	5.06	6.34	-21.61	4.12	-34.31	-7.92	-2.28	1.42	10.47
1994	174.19	98.61	226.62	29.89	351.92	181.65	175.48	32.58	46.38
1995	47.30	18.09	59.70	8.26	105.22	38.34	53.67	7.99	13.01
1996	61.56	-40.50	-25.26	-0.99	-85.05	-19.08	-12.22	-1.96	1.24
1997	62.86	54.30	65.12	13.75	101.41	49.39	45.62	5.96	26.81
1998	35.04	12.27	45.45	8.46	60.29	22.11	40.07	6.07	3.57
1999	18.92	4.24	18.13	-0.08	5.47	4.44	11.28	-2.77	8.23
2000	16.54	1.04	7.27	5.81	-37.44	10.06	13.75	2.91	-6.08
2001	37.61	1.93	47.67	24.10	105.56	48.09	39.05	14.95	14.79
2002	-54.88	-50.66	-124.59	-13.17	-167.02	-44.85	-139.04	-11.07	-6.70
2003	111.35	70.11	148.59	21.65	199.59	143.46	94.21	11.93	41.89
2004	15.64	29.45	4.00	1.72	-1.23	-1.18	3.58	-0.62	12.84
2005	19.12	18.33	24.24	2.03	53.86	16.87	26.47	1.29	15.69
2006	55.78	36.47	73.46	13.33	169.81	69.00	60.35	12.82	37.52
2007	42.38	28.65	68.12	10.53	140.09	75.42	51.35	8.93	28.68

Details of medium irrigation schemes of lakhpata

sr no	NAME OF DAM	AREA OF CATCHMENT IN m ²
1	Godhatad	188000000
2	Nara	233000000
3	Sanandro	148000000
4	Gajansar	166000000
	total catchment area	735000000

Details of minor irrigation schemes of lakhpata

SR NO.	NAME OF SCHEME	TALUKA	CATCHMENT AREA IN SQ. MILE	MEAN ANNUAL RAINFALL IN INCHES	GROSS STORAGE CAPACITY (MCM)	LIVE STORAGE CAPACITY (MCM)
1	Bhadhra	Lakhpat	26.00	14.30	7.19	5.25
2	Bhekhado	Lakhpat	5.35	11.90	1.49	1.17
3	Baranda	Lakhpat	8.50	13.75	3.11	1.64
4	Dhareshi	Lakhpat	21.70	14.95	2.42	2.42
5	Dedrani	Lakhpat	6.55	13.20	0.43	0.43
6	Fulara	Lakhpat	14.00	11.80	5.56	5.56
7	Gopalwari wandh	Lakhpat	3.50	9.40	0.69	0.97
8	Guhar	Lakhpat	-	-	-	-
9	Junachoy	Lakhpat	3.00	19.80	0.01	0.01
10	Kanoj	Lakhpat	7.00	11.80	2.63	1.27
11	Koriyani	Lakhpat	7.75	10.40	2.70	1.26
12	Lakhpat	Lakhpat	2.00	8.35	13.44	0.30
	Meghpar	Lakhpat	7.83	13.85	0.28	0.21
	Maniara	Lakhpat	3.72	11.70	0.02	0.55
	Morchabana	Lakhpat	3.80	12.20	0.68	0.47

Details of check dams of lakhpat

SR NO	CIRCLE CODE	CHK_CODE	ADM_CODE	CHK_LAT	CHK_LONG	TALUKA	VILLAGE	CHK_LENGTH
13	KIC	06	10-03-21-108	23°-15'-02	69°-20'-01	Lakhpat	Guneri	75
56	KIC	PANCH-KTC-06-054-004	10-05-22-000	230 -29' -00"	680 -43' --00"	Lakhpat	Kharai	20
67	KIC	PANCH-KTC-06-028-004	10-05-21-000	220 -45' -30"	680 -51' --00"	Lakhpat	Fulara	2
111	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 70-003	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Mindhiyari	15
112	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 77-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Nahara	14
113	KIC	SP-KTC-6--001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Chamara	15
185	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 81-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Panandhro	15
186	KIC	SP-KTC-6- ...-005	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Chamara	10
277	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 18-003	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Dayapar	15
278	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 18-002	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Dayapar	15
279	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 87-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Rodasasr	15

280	KIC	SP-KTC-6--003	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Chamara	15
299	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 28-003	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Fulra	15
317	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 70-002	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Mindhiyari	10
327	KIC	SP-KTC-6--004	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Chamara	15
345	KIC	SP-KTC-6--002	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Chamara	10
384	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 13-004	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Bhudha	22
385	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 07-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Baranda	22
400	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 09-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	BhadaraNana	10
415	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 31-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Gugariyana	20
421	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 18-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Dayapar	15
428	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 18-005	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Dayapar	23
438	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 08-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	BhadaraMota	10
445	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 97-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Subhaspar	10
464	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 13-002	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Bhudha	15
471	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 13-005	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Bhudha	22
472	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 79-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Narad (Bhudha)	22
473	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 30-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Godhatad	22
483	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 77-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Nara	10
502	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 18-004	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Dayapar	20
518	KIC	SP-KTC-16- 81-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Panandhro	15
527	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 09-003	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	BhadaraNana	15
528	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 08-004	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	BhadaraNana	10
529	KIC	SP-KTC-6--006	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Chamara	10
544	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 10-002	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Baiyava	10
580	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 13-003	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Bhudha	20
612	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 47-002	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Kanoj	10
614	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 10-003	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Baiyava	10
626	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 67-001	10-01-01-03		Lakhpat	Maldo	10

661	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 09-002	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	BhadaraNana	10
674	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 28-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Fulra	10
677	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 28-002	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Fulra	12
685	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 87-002	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Rodasar	20
687	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 70-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Mindhiyari	9
722	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 08-003	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	BhadaraNana	10
742	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 10-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Baiyava	10
744	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 13-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Bhudha	15
745	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 51-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Kharai	15
757	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 08-002	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	BhadaraNana	5
769	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 18-006	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Dayapar	14
774	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 41-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Zumara	15
816	KIC	06	10-03-21-109	23°-15'-04	69°-20'-02	Lakhpat	Guhar	30
819	KIC	PANCH-KTC-06-025-001	10-05-21-000	230 -37' -30"	680 -55' -00"	Lakhpat	Dolatpar	13
820	KIC	SP-KTC-6- 47-001	10-01-01-03			Lakhpat	Kanoj	7
824	KIC	PANCH-KTC-06-083-001	10-05-21-000	230 -33' -00"	680 -53' -30"	Lakhpat	Ravreshwar	20
899	KIC	06	10-03-21-107	23°-15'-01	69°-20'-00	Lakhpat	Rodasar	23
918	KIC	PANCH-KTC-06-010-001	10-05-21-000	230 -40' -30"	690 -06' -00"	Lakhpat	Zara-Jumara	15

total catch area of medium irri in m2	total catch area of minor irri in m2	total catch area of checkdams in m2	total catch area of surface storage in m2	suit area fraction gazeteer	suit area fraction landuse	area in m2 gazeteer	area in m2 landuse
735000000	312611564.9	354450000	1402061565	0.158532	0.12507086	1886060000	2.39E+09

year	rainfall in mm	LOG10Re	Re IN MM	Re in mm from suit area gazeteer	Re in mm from suit area landuse
1989	458.00	1.65	44.39	33.00	26.04
1990	97.50	-0.07	0.86	0.64	0.50
1991	0.00	-1.29	0.05	0.04	0.03
1992	650.00	1.88	75.03	55.77	44.00
1993	0.00	-1.29	0.05	0.04	0.03
1994	642.00	1.87	74.01	55.02	43.40
1995	110.00	0.05	1.13	0.84	0.66
1996	4.00	-1.23	0.06	0.04	0.03
1997	332.00	1.34	21.71	16.14	12.73
1998	58.00	-0.50	0.32	0.24	0.19
1999	0.00	-1.29	0.05	0.04	0.03
2000	0.00	-1.29	0.05	0.04	0.03
2001	0.00	-1.29	0.05	0.04	0.03
2002	58.00	-0.50	0.32	0.24	0.19
2003	1317.00	2.02	105.47	78.40	61.85
2004	267.00	1.09	12.24	9.10	7.18
2005	108.00	0.03	1.08	0.80	0.63
2006	656.00	1.88	75.78	56.33	44.44
2007	360.00	1.42	26.45	19.66	15.51

5.9.2 Recharge Due To Surface Storage

The groundwater recharge occurring due to surface storage structures has been worked out for all the talukas. Sufficient data regarding the monitoring of the surface storage structures for was not available for all the structures i.e. medium irrigation schemes, minor irrigation schemes as well as check dams. Therefore, the rainfall values and the catchment areas of the surface storage structures have been used to find out the recharge depth occurring due to the surface storage.

Sharda et al (2006) have developed a formula for the estimation of recharge depth from surface storage structures in semi-arid climate of India. It gives the value of recharge depth due to surface storage in mm if value of rainfall in mm is known. The formula is as follows:

$$\text{Log}_{10}R_e = a(b-e^{-cP})$$

Where

R_e = recharge in mm due to the surface storage

P = rainfall in mm

$a = 3.322$ (constant)

$b = 0.611$ (constant)

$$c = 4.72 \times 10^{-3} \text{ (constant)}$$

The values for a, b and c obtained by them have been used here as the surface conditions for their study are comparable to the surface conditions of the study area at Kutch.

The recharge value in mm thus obtained was then multiplied by the fraction obtained by the ratio of the total catchment area of all the surface storage structures in a taluka to that of the total area of the taluka to obtain the recharge depth due to surface storage structures. The values for the recharge due to surface storage structures for all the talukas have been tabulated in Table 5. 28.

Table 5.28 Groundwater Recharge Depth in mm due to Surface Storage Structures

Year	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpat	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakha-trana	Naliya	Rapar
1989	25.46	12.13	22.66	26.04	71.45	62.08	29.10	66.99	52.12
1990	5.98	3.37	5.32	0.50	1.38	1.20	0.56	1.29	1.01
1991	0.82	0.25	0.73	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.08	0.06
1992	31.51	0.66	28.04	44.00	120.76	104.92	49.18	113.22	88.08
1993	1.59	0.05	1.42	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.08	0.06
1994	65.12	21.03	57.95	43.40	119.12	103.49	48.51	111.68	86.89
1995	4.48	1.10	3.98	0.66	1.82	1.58	0.74	1.71	1.33
1996	3.15	2.75	2.80	0.03	0.09	0.08	0.04	0.09	0.07
1997	54.90	12.55	48.85	12.73	34.94	30.35	14.23	32.76	25.48
1998	10.40	8.65	9.26	0.19	0.51	0.45	0.21	0.48	0.37
1999	0.69	3.58	0.62	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.08	0.06
2000	5.69	0.57	5.06	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.08	0.06
2001	11.13	0.01	9.90	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.08	0.06
2002	1.46	0.90	1.30	0.19	0.51	0.45	0.21	0.48	0.37
2003	62.99	16.10	56.05	61.85	169.75	147.48	69.13	159.16	123.82
2004	12.46	3.32	11.08	7.18	19.70	17.11	8.02	18.47	14.37
2005	20.38	8.08	18.14	0.63	1.74	1.51	0.71	1.63	1.27
2006	30.56	7.01	27.19	44.44	121.97	105.96	49.67	114.35	88.96
2007	46.06	17.50	40.99	15.51	42.57	36.98	17.34	39.91	31.05

5.9.3 Total Recharge

The total groundwater recharge was obtained by summing the values of groundwater recharge due to rainfall and the groundwater recharge due to surface storage structures. The values for the total recharge have been tabulated in Table 5.29. Once again the values of the recharge are negative for the years 1991, 1996 and 2002 indicating fall in the groundwater level for those years. This may be due to probability of excessive withdrawal of groundwater during those years

and that the values of recharge due to surface storage structures is less than the withdrawal in those years.

Table 5.29 Total Groundwater Recharge Depth in mm

Year	Anjar	Bhachau	Bhuj	Lakhpat	Mandvi	Mundra	Nakha-trana	Naliya	Rapar
1989	69.83	40.93	98.78	46.10	198.12	95.75	125.56	78.39	72.63
1990	38.41	16.49	38.29	8.37	19.37	19.53	29.71	5.72	12.51
1991	14.69	-0.10	3.45	0.25	8.24	0.37	5.61	0.91	-4.49
1992	122.45	67.70	217.29	90.00	334.10	178.68	214.43	141.21	118.00
1993	6.66	6.39	-20.19	4.15	-34.23	-7.85	-2.24	1.50	10.53
1994	239.31	119.64	284.56	73.29	471.04	285.14	223.99	144.27	133.26
1995	51.78	19.20	63.68	8.92	107.04	39.92	54.41	9.69	14.34
1996	64.71	-37.75	-22.46	-0.96	-84.96	-19.00	-12.18	-1.87	1.31
1997	117.76	66.85	113.97	26.48	136.35	79.74	59.85	38.71	52.29
1998	45.45	20.92	54.70	8.64	60.81	22.56	40.28	6.55	3.94
1999	19.62	7.82	18.74	-0.05	5.55	4.51	11.31	-2.70	8.29
2000	22.22	1.62	12.33	5.84	-37.36	10.13	13.79	2.99	-6.02
2001	48.73	1.94	57.57	24.13	105.64	48.16	39.08	15.02	14.85
2002	-53.43	-49.76	-123.30	-12.98	-166.51	-44.41	-138.83	-10.59	-6.33
2003	174.34	86.21	204.64	83.50	369.34	290.94	163.34	171.09	165.71
2004	28.10	32.77	15.08	8.90	18.46	15.93	11.60	17.84	27.20
2005	39.50	26.41	42.38	2.67	55.60	18.39	27.18	2.92	16.96
2006	86.33	43.48	100.65	57.78	291.78	174.96	110.02	127.18	126.48
2007	88.44	46.15	109.11	26.04	182.65	112.40	68.68	48.85	59.73

5.10 SUMMARY FOR GROUNDWATER ANALYSIS

The above figures for the water level fluctuations for all the talukas show that for the study period of 1989 to 2007, the water level for post-monsoon is higher than the water level for pre-monsoon for almost all years except 1991, 1996 and 2002. During the year 2001, there was a major earthquake in Kutch which had resulted in the damage to almost all the surface storage structures. These structures were repaired subsequently with priority being given to the structures which were used for water supply. This may have resulted in excessive withdrawal of groundwater. The years 1991 and 1996 have the annual rainfall values less than 50% of the average annual rainfall for the region, which may have resulted in excessive withdrawal of groundwater. This is also reflected in the values of total groundwater recharge as shown in Table 5.29 as the values of the total groundwater recharge for the years 1991, 1996 and 2002 show negative values.

Individual analysis of the water level fluctuation for the wells shows that levels of the wells located in the vicinity of any surface storage structure like a medium irrigation scheme, minor

irrigation scheme or check dam have comparatively more rise in the water level as compared to those located away from these structures.

5.1 Draft Pattern

The analysis of the draft in mm for obtaining the mean values, minimum values, maximum values, variance, standard deviation and the standard error was done for the annual values for the period of 1989 to 2007 using the software Statistica. The results for the analysis have been tabulated in Table 5.30.

Table 5.30 Results for Draft Values (mm) for 1989 to 2007

Taluka	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Variance	Std.Dev.	Standard Error
Anjar	54.85	47.83	29.65	101.00	473.90	21.77	4.87
Bhachau	37.07	32.96	0.94	101.00	503.97	22.45	5.02
Bhuj	46.65	36.91	12.44	114.19	803.56	28.35	6.34
Lakhpat	20.01	14.63	-20.67	99.71	670.03	25.88	5.94
Mandvi	55.97	43.65	31.38	108.00	539.86	23.23	5.33
Mundra	53.94	48.50	24.50	112.74	503.26	22.43	5.15
Nakhatrana	44.63	40.91	-0.15	106.18	743.73	27.27	6.26
Naliya	29.02	20.32	0.51	88.77	670.64	25.90	5.94
Rapar	31.76	29.02	3.03	71.95	316.00	17.78	4.08

5.2 Total Groundwater Recharge

The analysis of total annual groundwater recharge depth in mm for obtaining the mean values, minimum values, maximum values, variance, standard deviation and the standard error was done for the annual values for the period of 1989 to 2007 using the software Statistica. The results for the analysis have been tabulated in Table 5.31.

Table 5.31 Results for Annual Groundwater Recharge Values (mm) for 1989 to 2007

Taluka	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Variance	Std.Dev.	Standard Error
Anjar	64.47	48.73	-53.43	239.31	4268.67	65.34	14.99
Bhachau	27.21	20.92	-49.76	119.64	1627.21	40.34	9.25
Bhuj	66.80	54.70	-123.30	284.56	8918.79	94.44	21.67
Lakhpat	24.27	8.90	-12.98	90.00	956.20	30.92	7.09
Mandvi	107.42	60.81	-166.51	471.04	27485.15	165.79	38.03
Mundra	69.78	22.56	-44.41	290.94	9557.90	97.76	22.43
Nakhatrana	55.03	39.08	-138.83	223.99	7172.41	84.69	19.43
Naliya	41.98	9.69	-10.59	171.09	3533.23	59.44	13.64
Rapar	43.22	14.85	-6.33	165.71	2951.52	54.33	12.46